

Synthesis and antifungal screening of some new 1,3-diketo amino analogues

Anand K. Halve*, Poonam Gour, Rakesh Dubey, Deepti Bhaduria and Bhuwan Bhaskar

School of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji University, Gwalior-474 011, India

E-mail : drhalve_chemjiwaji@rediffmail.com

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Few new 1,3-diketo amino compounds containing -NH-N=C< linkage have been synthesized by incorporating chloro group at different positions and are reported along with their spectral data and antifungal properties.

Certain natural and synthetic 1,3-diketo amino structural analogues have attracted special interest by virtue of their varied and pharmaceutically useful biological actions as antimicrobial, anticancer and anti-HIV agents¹. Acid-hydrazides of malonanilic acid series and several derivatives of hydrazones containing diketo moiety and -NH-N=C< linkage are well known for their demonstrable therapeutic efficacy². In connection with our current interest, in this paper, we present the synthetic strategy of some new 1,3-diketo amino analogues, incorporating chloro group at different positions via two different approaches. The antifungal profile of some of the synthesized compounds has also been studied.

Results and discussion

Two new series of hydrazones namely, *N*-1',3'-diketopropanephényl amine-3-methoxy-4-acetyloxyphenyl hydrazone **1(ii)** and 2'-hydroxy-5'-(phenyl azo)-*N*-(1,3-diketophenyl amine) hydrazone **3(ii)** were obtained by the condensation of 3-methoxy-4-acetyloxybenzaldehyde **1(i)** and 2-hydroxy-5-(phenylazo)benzaldehyde **3(i)** with corresponding malonanilic acid hydrazide **2** respectively, as depicted in Scheme 1. All the products [**1(ii)** and **3(ii)**] are crystalline solids having sharp melting points, soluble in dimethyl formamide and ethanol and have been characterized by spectral studies.

Antifungal activity :

Compound **1(ii)a-d** and **3(ii)m-p** were screened *in vitro* for their antifungal activity against five fungal pathogens namely *A. niger* (VPCI-3), *A. flavus* (VPCI-5), *A. fumigatus* (VPCI-2), *C. albicans* (VPCI-15) and *C. neoformans* (VPCI-10) by using serial dilution tube technique as described earlier³. Concentrations varying from 15.62 to 4000 µg/ml of each compound, were prepared by dissolving the compounds in DMF using Sabouraud's Dextrose media and results were compared with that of

Scheme 1

Table 1. Antifungal screening data of compounds 1(ii)a-d and 3(ii)m-p

Compd.	R	R'	<i>A. niger</i> (μg)	<i>A. flavus</i> (μg)	<i>A. fumigatus</i> (μg)	<i>C. neoformans</i> (μg)	<i>C. albicans</i> (μg)
1(ii)a	-	H	4000 (2000)	4000 (2000)	2000 (1000)	4000 (2000)	2000 (1000)
b	-	Cl(o)	4000 (2000)	4000 (2000)	2000 (1000)	500 (250)	4000 (2000)
c	-	Cl(m)	4000 (2000)	2000 (1000)	1000 (500)	4000 (2000)	4000 (2000)
d	-	Cl(p)	4000 (2000)	4000 (2000)	500 (250)	250 (125)	4000 (2000)
3(ii)m	Cl(p)	H	4000 (2000)	4000 (2000)	4000 (2000)	500 (250)	4000 (2000)
n	Cl(p)	Cl(o)	4000 (2000)	4000 (2000)	4000 (2000)	500 (250)	4000 (2000)
o	Cl(p)	Cl(m)	2000 (1000)	4000 (2000)	4000 (2000)	2000 (1000)	4000 (2000)
p	Cl(p)	Cl(p)	2000 (1000)	4000 (2000)	4000 (2000)	62.5 (31.25)	4000 (2000)
Fluconazole			4000 (2000)	2000 (1000)	4000 (2000)	500 (250)	4000 (2000)

Figures without parenthesis indicate fungicidal and within parenthesis indicate fungistatic.

control drug - Fluconazole. A systematic perusal of data presented in Table 1. Amongst the tested compounds, 1(ii)d exhibited maximum activity against *A. fumigatus* and *C. neoformans*. Compound 3(ii)p showed highest activity against *C. neoformans* while significant activity against *A. niger*. The results of antifungal screening reveals that incorporation of chloro pharmacophore at para position in the synthesized compounds, increases the antifungal activity.

Experimental

All the commercial reagents used were of A.R. grade and distilled by common methods. Melting points were determined on an electric melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 337 Infra cord spectrometer and ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) on a varian EM-390 MHz spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard.

3-Methoxy-4-acetyloxybenzaldehyde 1(i): 3-Methoxy-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.35 M) was dissolved in aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (2.5 N). Acetic anhydride (15 ml) was added in the reaction mixture which was constantly stirred for 1 h at 0°C. The solid was filtered, washed with sodium hydroxide solution (20 ml, 0.1 N) and distilled water and recrystallised from petroleum ether

(60–80°C). Yield, 58%; m.p. 62°C, $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$ (Found : C, 61.72; H, 5.10. Calcd. for : C, 61.85; H, 5.15%); IR (KBr) ν cm^{-1} 1690 (C=O, aldehydic), 1757 (C=O, acetyloxy), 1280 and 1032 (-OCH₃); ^1H NMR δ (DMSO- d_6) 8.9 (1H, s, CHO), 2.6 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.3 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 7.0–7.8 (3H, m, aromatic protons).

2-Hydroxy-5-(p-chlorophenylazo)benzaldehyde 3(i)d: Aniline (0.04 M) was dissolved in aqueous hydrochloric acid (6 N) and mechanically stirred at 0–5°C. The cold solution of sodium nitrite was added to constantly stirred reaction mixture drop by drop. The diazotized solution was immediately added in small portions in salicylaldehyde, dissolved in aqueous sodium hydroxide (6 N) during constant stirring at 0–5°C. The stirring was continued for 4 h. The solid obtained, was filtered under suction washed with cold water and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid. Yield, 65%, m.p. 200°C, $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$ (Found : C, 59.03; H, 3.36; N, 10.70. Calcd. for : C, 59.81; H, 3.45; N, 10.74%); IR (KBr) ν cm^{-1} 1666 (C=O aldehydic), 3430 (-OH), 1600 (N=N); ^1H NMR δ (DMSO- d_6) 9.2 (1H, s, CHO), 6.0 (1H, s, OH), 7.2–7.7 (7H, m, aromatic protons). Similarly other compounds were prepared 3(i)a, m.p. 126°; b, 122° and c, 136° in 60–78% yield.

o-, *m*- and *p*-chloro substituted malonanilic acid hydrazides **2** have been prepared by the reported methods⁴.

N-1',3'-Diketo propane-4-chloro-phenyl amine-3-methoxy-4-acetyloxy phenyl hydrazone **1(ii)d** : An equimolecular mixture (0.005 M) of compound **1(i)** and **2** was refluxed in ethanol for 2 h and left aside in an ice bath. The resulting precipitate was filtered off and recrystallised from petroleum ether (60–80°C). Yield 58%; m.p. 214°, C₁₉H₁₈N₃O₅Cl (Found : C, 56.42; H, 4.43; N, 10.35. Calcd. for : C, 56.50; H, 4.46; N, 10.40%); IR (KBr) ν cm⁻¹ 3400 (NH), 1620 (CH=N), 1280 and 1030 (OCH₃), 1770 (C=O, acetyloxy), 1660 and 2780 (C=O, 1,3-diketo); ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 9.8 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.7 (1H, s, NH^a), 7.0 (1H, s, NH^b), 3.6 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.4 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 4.0 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.2–7.6 (7H, m, aromatic protons).

Similarly other compounds were prepared **1(ii)a**, 161°; **b**, 152° and **c**, 178° in 58–68% yield.

2'-Hydroxy-5'-(4-chloro phenyl azo)-*N*-(1,3-diketo-4-chloro phenyl amine)hydrazone **3(ii)p** : It has been prepared by the method adopted for the preparation of **1(ii)d**. Yield, 62%, m.p. 122°, C₂₂H₁₇N₅O₃Cl₂ (Found : C, 56.12; H, 3.60; N, 14.82. Calcd. for : C, 56.17; H, 3.61; N, 14.89%); IR (KBr) ν cm⁻¹ 3560 (OH), 3400 (NH), 1630 (CH=N), 1600 (N=N), 1650 and 2780 (C=O, 1,3-diketo); ¹H NMR δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 9.6 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.2 (1H, s, NH^a), 6.9 (1H, s, NH^b), 5.3 (1H, s, OH), 4.2 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.3–7.9 (11H, m, aromatic protons).

Similarly other compounds were prepared **3(ii)a**, m.p. 125°; **b**, 180°; **c**, 160°; **d**, 170°; **e**, 182°; **f**, 156°; **g**, 194°; **h**, 222°; **i**, 132°; **j**, 162°; **k**, 190°; **l**, 182°; **m**, 130°; **n**, 85° and **o**, 138° in 60–75% yields.

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References

1. S. Guernelli, M. F. Lagana, D. Spinelli, P. Lo Meo, R. Noto and S. Riela, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2002, **67**, 2948; A. De Logu, V. Onnis, B. Saggi, C. Congieu, M. L. Schivo and M. T. Cocco, *J. Antimicrob. Chemother.*, 2002, **49**, 275; L. Savini, L. Chiasserini, A. Gaeta and C. Pellerano, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2002, **10**, 2193; P. Vicini, F. Zani, P. Colzini and I. Doytchinova, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2002, **37**, 553; A. Walcourt, M. Loyevsky, D. B. Lovejoy, V. R. Gordeuk and D. R. Richardson, *Int. J. Biochem. Cell Biol.*, 2004, **36**, 461; S. Papakonstantinou-Garoufalias, N. Pauli, P. Marakos and A. Chytiroglou-Ladas, *Farmaco*, 2002, **57**, 973; L. R. Morgan, K. Thangaraj, B. Le Blanc, A. Rodgers, L. T. Wolford, C. L. Hooper, D. Fan and B. S. Jursic, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2003, **46**, 4552; A. Andreani, M. Granaiola, A. Leoni, A. Locatelli, R. Morigi, M. Rambaldi, G. Giorgi and V. Garaliene, *Anticancer Res.*, 2004, **24**, 203; L. Corre, F. Dujols, J. Bastide, F. Collignon, B. Lesur, A. Frydman and F. Darro, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2003, **46**, 3536; V. S. Jolly and K. P. Sharma *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 412.
2. K. Mogilaiah, R. H. Babu, R. Babu Rao and V. N. Reddy, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 218; S. Shah and R. H. Mehta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 241; I. Mir, M. T. Siddiqui and A. Comrie, *Tetrahedron*, 1970, **26**, 5235; M. E. Furrow and A. G. Myers, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **126**, 5436; T. G. Custer, S. Kato, V. M. Bierbaum, C. J. Howard and G. C. Morrison, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **126**, 2744; E. Lattova, H. Perreault and O. Krokhin, *J. Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom.*, 2004, **15**, 725; G. R. Cook, B. C. Maity and R. Kargbo, *Org. Lett.*, 2004, **6**, 1741; I. E. I. Kaim, L. Grimaud, Y. Perroux and C. Tirla, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2003, **68**, 8733.
3. R. Cruickshank, J. P. Duguid and R. H. A. Swain, "Medical Microbiology", The English Language Book Society & E & S Living Stone Ltd., 1969, 893.
4. B. S. Rathore and P. J. Ittyerah, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 591.